

ISic1013

I.Sicily inscription 1013

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Vigna Cassia

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. εἰκόνι κ[---τύ]πῳ μ' ἐπ[---]σαι
2. σεμνοαπρεπῶς βιότοιο χρόνους τε[λέσασαν ἀμέμ]πτως
3. [---]ΛΩΧΑ μοι σοί τε τὰ καί με [ἀγ]απήσας
4. Σ[---] φιλείης μορφὴν ΗΙΣ [ἔ]δ,ειξεν ὁμοίαν

Apparatus

Text of IG with slight changes based on Kaibel's diplomatic transcription

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492640

EDCS 39102167

PHI 140491

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0193 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1013. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4351402>